

Welcome to the sixth edition of the ENTRUST newsletter! Since January 2025, there have been several interesting activities that our consortium has been involved in. Discover more and get the latest updates about the project in this edition of our newsletter.

As the ENTRUST project progresses and apart from the technical advancements, we would like to showcase our engagement and participation in significant Webinars, Workshops, and Events. Of course, our presence on social media is highlighted by kickstarting campaigns to share our activities and engage more stakeholders, while providing insightful blogs about the work being done!

ENTRUST Webinars

Through a series of open training activities, ENTRUST aims to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical implementation by showcasing its open-source developments, methodologies, and tools.

[Learn more](#)

ENTRUST 5th Plenary Meeting in Athens

On May 21st-22nd, the EnTrust Project consortium gathered for the **5th Plenary Meeting**, hosted by UniSystems in Athens, Greece. Over two productive days, all project partners focused on reviewing the progress of technical activities, assessing integration steps across use cases, and aligning on the roadmap for the final stretch of the project.

[Learn more](#)

Latest from our blog

[Open-source framework could help Europe strengthen medical device security](#)

[Advancing Threat Modeling in the ENTRUST Project](#)

[Navigating the Final Frontier: ENTRUST's Final Year in Action](#)

[Digital assistance to improve the health and well-being of patients and carers](#)

[Enhancing Security in Connected Medical Devices](#)

[Improving security and privacy through profiles and conformity certification](#)

[Formal Verification: Ensuring Security in Connected Medical Devices](#)

[Enhancing Connected Medical Device Security with Digital Twins and AI-Based Anomaly Detection](#)

[Ensuring Runtime Trust in Connected Medical Devices](#)

Events

[ENTRUST at HIMSS25 Europe in Paris](#)

[ENTRUST at Nexus Luxembourg 2025](#)

[ENTRUST at BEYOND Expo 2025: Showcasing Innovation in Athens](#)

[Workshop: Innovative Solutions for Cyber Risk in Medical Devices](#)

[A co-creation workshop: ENTRUST & AI4LUNGS](#)

Partners

